

Performance Of Administrative Officers Among Elementary Schools: A Basis For A Technical Assistance Plan

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Abstract

The performance of administrative officers in the Second District of Sto. Niño's elementary schools was investigated in this study. For the 2024–2025 school year, Sto. Niño, Cagayan will serve as the foundation for a technical assistance plan. A validated questionnaire was used to gather data from 63 respondents, including administrative officers, school heads, and presidents of School Parent-Teachers Associations (SPTAs), using a descriptive-comparative-correlational approach. Frequency, percentage, weighted mean, ANOVA, and Chi-square test with Cramer's V were among the statistical methods used.

The findings showed that administrative officers are typically young, primarily female, with bachelor's degrees and little training experience. They received very high ratings for their work in the areas of financial management, general administrative assistance, property custodianship, and personnel administration (overall mean = 4.78). Chi-square results revealed no significant correlation between performance and profile characteristics, and ANOVA results showed no significant difference in performance assessments among responder groups ($p > 0.05$). Despite excellent performance, issues like heavy workloads, complicated financial reporting, inadequate training, and ICT limitations were noted. To solve these problems and maintain efficient administrative performance, a technical assistance plan was put forth.

Keywords: *Technical Assistance Plan, Administrative Officers, Duties, Performance Assessment*

Introduction

Administrative officers were essential to the smooth functioning of elementary schools in the contemporary educational environment. They played a crucial role in managing resources, personnel, and finances, thereby influencing the overall success of the educational system. As the demands for accountability and efficiency in school management increased, evaluating the performance of administrative officers became an important area of concern among educators and policymakers. Administrative officers performed various managerial and support functions that directly affected school operations. Beyond clerical tasks, they managed personnel, oversaw assets, ensured accurate financial documentation, and provided administrative support to school leaders. Regular assessment of their performance was necessary to identify strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement.

In the Second District of Sto. Niño, Cagayan, elementary schools faced unique challenges that could affect the effectiveness of their administrative staff. These challenges included limited financial resources, inadequate training opportunities, and evolving policy requirements. Understanding how administrative officers navigated these obstacles was essential in developing a technical assistance plan that addressed their needs and enhanced their performance. Without proper intervention, inefficiencies in administrative tasks could hinder school operations and ultimately affect the quality of education provided to students. Despite the crucial role played by administrative officers in school management, there was a scarcity of studies focusing on their performance in elementary education within the Second District of Sto. Niño, Cagayan. While existing literature underscored the importance of administrative efficiency in education, a gap remained in assessing the specific challenges encountered by administrative staff and in identifying the technical support necessary to enhance their competencies. In addition, many studies emphasized the effectiveness of school leaders and teachers, while giving limited attention to the vital role of administrative staff in the educational system.

These studies shed light on the role and performance of administrative officers in Philippine elementary schools, emphasizing the significance of regular performance assessments, professional development programs, and the specific challenges encountered in rural settings.

Building on these findings, this study was conducted in the Second District of Sto. Niño, Cagayan, to evaluate the performance of administrative officers and to propose a tailored technical assistance plan for elementary schools in the municipality. Some administrative officers and school heads handled more than one school, a practice commonly referred to as clustering. The study aimed to enhance administrative practices and improve the overall effectiveness of elementary schools in rural areas.

The study was also anchored on the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4, specifically United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4: Quality Education, which aimed to ensure inclusive, equitable, quality education and to promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. By managing schools effectively, maintaining accurate records, coordinating resources, and providing administrative support to teachers and school administrators, administrative officers contributed significantly to the successful delivery of educational services. Their performance greatly supported the effective implementation of school programs and the attainment of

educational objectives. This study contributed to the advancement of effective educational governance and institutional efficiency by evaluating the performance of administrative officers in elementary schools. Furthermore, the proposed technical assistance plan was intended to support the realization of quality education and sustainable institutional development by strengthening administrative competencies, enhancing workplace performance, and improving the quality of services provided within the school system.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the performance of administrative officers of elementary schools in Second District of Sto Nino, Cagayan for the Calendar Year 2024-2025, as a basis for a technical assistance plan.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the administrative officer respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Sex
 - 1.3 Civil Status
 - 1.4 Highest Educational Attainment
 - 1.5 Plantilla Position
 - 1.6 Length of Service
 - 1.7 Number of Relevant Learning and Development programs and activities attended
2. How do the administrative officer-respondents perform their duties as assessed by the three groups of respondents relative to:
 - 2.1 Personnel Administration
 - 2.2 Property Custodianship
 - 2.3 General Administrative Support
 - 2.4 Financial Management
3. Is there a significant difference on the performance of the administrative officer-respondents as assess by the three groups of respondents?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the performance of the administrative officer-respondents and their profile variables?
5. What are the challenges and issues encountered by the administrative officer-respondents in performing their duties?
6. What technical assistance plan can be proposed to address the challenges and issues encountered by the administrative officer-respondents in performing their duties?

METHODS

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive-inferential research design, specifically employing the descriptive-comparative-correlational approach. The descriptive approach was used to determine the demographic profile of the respondents, their assessment of the performance of administrative officers in the discharge of their duties, and the challenges and issues encountered by the administrative officer-respondents in performing their responsibilities. In addition, the comparative approach was used to examine the differences in the performance of the administrative officer-respondents as assessed by the three groups of respondents. Finally, the correlational approach was used to determine the relationship between the performance of the administrative officer-respondents and their profile variables.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were the administrative officers, School Heads, and School Parents-Teachers Association (SPTA) Presidents of the elementary schools in the Second District of Sto. Niño, Cagayan for the School Year 2024–2025. Some administrative officers and school heads were assigned to more than one school, a practice commonly referred to as clustering. A total of 29 elementary schools in the district corresponded to the total number of SPTA Presidents included in the study. The respondents were selected using the total enumeration method, and their distribution was presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Distribution of Respondents

Respondents	Population(N)	Percentage (%)
School Heads	17	27.00
Administrative Officers	17	27.00
SPTA	29	46.00
Total	63	100.00

Data Gathering Tool

This study utilized a questionnaire checklist that was constructed by the researcher and validated by experts prior to the gathering of pertinent data.

The first part of the instrument covered the profile variables of the respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, Plantilla position, length of service, and the number of relevant learning and development programs and activities attended.

The second part consisted of a questionnaire that assessed the performance of administrative officers in the discharge of their duties. It was composed of ten (10) statements for each of the following dimensions: personnel administration, property custodianship, general administrative support, and financial management.

The questionnaire underwent validity and reliability testing to ensure its appropriateness and consistency as a data-gathering instrument.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data gathering procedure began with the development of a researcher-made questionnaire, which was validated by the panel members. After the content validation, the researcher conducted a pilot test of the questionnaire among the school heads, administrative officers, and School Parents-Teachers Association (SPTA) Presidents of elementary schools in another district of Sto. Niño, Cagayan.

Once the questionnaire was found to be valid and reliable through pilot testing, the researcher secured ethical clearance from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) by complying with the clarifications, findings, and recommendations raised during the proposal defense and the expedited review of the manuscript by the members of the board. A certificate of approval to conduct the study was also obtained from the Office of the Dean of the Graduate School, School of Liberal Arts and Teacher Education, University of Cagayan Valley, indicating that the study had been approved and was ready for implementation.

After obtaining approval from the university authorities, the researcher sent a formal letter of request to the Public Schools District Supervisor (PSDS), or district-in-charge, to seek permission to conduct the study in the identified schools.

Upon receiving the necessary approvals, the researcher oriented the respondents regarding the purpose of the study. The written approvals from the appropriate authorities were presented, and a confidentiality agreement was formally established between the researcher and the respondents.

After the data had been gathered, the responses were tabulated, recorded, and analyzed.

Statistical Tools

The researcher utilized the following statistical tools to attain the objectives of the study.

Frequency count and percentage were used to determine the demographic profile of the respondents.

Weighted mean was used to assess the performance of administrative officers in the discharge of their duties and was further interpreted using the scale presented below.

Numerical Scale	Mean Range	Descriptive Interpretation
5	4.20-5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.40-4.19	Agree
3	2.60-3.39	Neutral
2	1.80-2.59	Disagree
1	1.00-1.79	Strongly Disagree

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was utilized to test the differences in the performance of the administrative officer-respondents in the discharge of their duties as assessed by the three groups of respondents.

The Chi-square test using Cramér's V was utilized to determine the relationship between the performance of the administrative officer-respondents and their profile variables. Frequency count and rank were utilized to identify the challenges and issues encountered by the administrative officer-respondents in performing their duties.

Summary of Findings

Based on the data gathered and analyzed, the following findings were derived in accordance with the specific objectives of the study.

1. Profile of Administrative Officers

- The majority of the administrative officers were within the age range of 30–34 years, indicating a relatively young workforce.
- Most of the respondents were female and married.
- In terms of educational attainment, the majority held bachelor's degrees, while a smaller proportion had master's degrees.
- All respondents occupied the Administrative Officer II position.
- Most had 1–3 years of service, and a significant number had attended only one relevant training program.

2. Performance of Administrative Officers

2.1 Personnel Administration

- Administrative officers demonstrated a “very high” level of performance in personnel administration.

2.2 Property Custodianship

- Administrative officers demonstrated a “very high” level of performance in property custodianship.

2.3 General Administrative Support

- Administrative officers demonstrated a “very high” level of performance in general administrative support.

2.4 Financial Management

- Administrative officers demonstrated a “very high” level of performance in financial management.

3. Difference in Performance Assessment

- There was no significant difference in the performance ratings of administrative officers as assessed by the administrative officers themselves, school heads, and SPTA Presidents.

4. Relationship Between Performance and Profile Variables

- There was no significant relationship between the performance of administrative officers and their profile variables such as age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, length of service, and training attended.

5. Challenges and Issues Encountered

- Workload pressure and multiple deadlines (e.g., multiple tasks, tight deadlines, time constraints, and overloaded workload)
- Financial and reporting complexities (e.g., liquidation, financial reports, budgeting, MOOE, and accounting tasks)
- Distance and accessibility issues (e.g., remote work locations, long distances from home, and difficulty reaching schools)
- Lack of training and experience (e.g., newly hired personnel requiring guidance and additional skills training)
- Resource and administrative challenges (e.g., handling multiple schools, lack of materials, and property management issues)
- Need for support and coordination (e.g., teamwork, communication, feedback, and cooperation)
- Adapting to new systems and policies (e.g., new guidelines, digital systems, and policy changes)
- ICT and technical limitations (e.g., poor internet connectivity and computer literacy issues)

Conclusion

Administrative officers in the Second District of Sto. Niño, Cagayan were generally young, qualified, and capable; however, they required continuous professional development to sustain and enhance their competencies. They demonstrated a very high level of performance across all key functional areas, which indicated the effective execution of their roles and responsibilities in school administration.

The absence of significant differences in the performance assessments made by administrative officers, school heads, and SPTA Presidents indicated strong agreement and reliability in the evaluation process, reflecting transparency and consistency in administrative practices. Likewise, the absence of a significant relationship between performance and profile variables suggested that performance was largely influenced by organizational systems, policies, and standardized procedures rather than by individual characteristics.

Despite the high performance' ratings, administrative officers encountered significant operational challenges, particularly workload pressure and multiple deadlines, financial and reporting complexities, distance and accessibility issues, lack of training and experience, resource and administrative challenges, the need for support and coordination, adaptation to new systems and policies, and ICT and technical limitations. These challenges could affect long-term efficiency if left unaddressed.

The proposed technical assistance plan was found to be essential and appropriate, as it directly addressed the identified gaps and supported the continuous improvement of administrative performance.

Recommendations:

In light of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were offered:

1. The Schools Division Office (SDO) of Cagayan may develop and implement a comprehensive and continuous training program for administrative officers focusing on financial management, personnel administration, and records management. They may also provide adequate technical support systems, including digital tools and updated administrative software, to improve efficiency and ensure timely release of financial resources to support smooth school operations.
2. The School Heads may strengthen mentoring and coaching mechanisms for administrative officers, particularly those with fewer years of experience. They may also promote workload distribution and task delegation to reduce administrative burden and encourage administrative officers to participate in professional development programs.
3. The Administrative Officers may actively engage in continuous learning and professional development opportunities to enhance competencies. They may also adopt efficient work practices and time management strategies to handle multiple responsibilities and utilize available resources and technologies to improve administrative processes.
4. The Policy Makers and DepEd Officials may allocate more funding for training programs and administrative capacity-building initiatives. They may also strengthen policies related to administrative support and resource allocation in schools and enhance monitoring systems to ensure effective implementation of administrative functions.
5. For Future Researchers they are encourage to conduct similar studies in other districts or regions to compare findings and validate results. They may also explore additional variables such as organizational culture, leadership styles, and job satisfaction that may influence administrative performance and investigate the long-term impact of technical assistance programs on administrative efficiency and school outcomes.

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